

**Prevention,
correction, and
valorisation of
exhaust flows
from urban photo
biorefineries**

14

Project
partners

9

European
countries

3

Demonstration
sites

About the Project

Across Europe, more than **26,000 wastewater treatment plants** and **5,800 municipal waste facilities** process waste from hundreds of millions of citizens. Yet the sector remains a significant source of **greenhouse gas emissions**, including methane and nitrous oxide.

Although circular solutions such as biogas and bio-based products exist, scalable technologies that fully convert urban waste, including diffuse emissions, into high-value resources are still lacking.

POST-PURPLE addresses this gap by developing a **novel photo-biorefinery approach** that transform gas, liquid and solid waste streams into valuable products, including microbial proteins, carotenoids, omega-3 fatty acids and green methanol.

By capturing up to **95% of CO₂** and **significantly reducing diffuse emissions**, the project aims to make urban biorefineries cleaner, more circular and substantially more sustainable, and to decrease heat emissions and reduce noise impact.

Demonstration Sites

POST-PURPLE showcases **real-world innovations in sustainable water and waste management.** Our demonstration sites highlight cutting-edge technologies that reduce emissions, recover valuable resources, and promote circular economy solutions.

Wastewater Treatment Plant
Badajoz, Spain

Thermal Hydrolysis of Organic Waste
Rivas-Vaciamadrid, Spain

Solid Urban Waste Treatment
Kozani, Greece

Our Goals

Resource Recovery

Nothing is waste. Everything is a resource.

We convert exhaust streams and solid residues into valuable bio-based products, renewable energy and carbon-storing materials.

- CO₂ and off-gas valorisation
- Syngas production and valorisation
- Biochar for carbon storage
- Heat recovery integration
- Photosynthetic-based biotechnological products

Emission Reduction

Cleaner processes. Lower impact.

We minimise diffuse emissions to air and water while improving environmental compliance and operational safety.

- Reduced air pollutants
- Lower water contamination
- Climate impact mitigation
- Regulatory alignment
- Odour treatment
- Reduced noise impact

Digital & Circular Intelligence

Smart optimisation through simulation.

We develop Digital Twins and a Decision Support System to model, optimise and validate sustainability performance before implementation.

- Real-time simulation
- Scenario testing
- Circularity assessment
- Data-driven investment support

Our Approach

POST-PURPLE implements a circular, iterative approach inspired by the Deming Cycle to advance urban biorefinery technologies. The methodology is structured into three main phases:

Analyse

Identify key challenges in wastewater and urban waste treatment. Reduce contaminants and discover new valuable compounds.

Develop

Tackle technical barriers, cut emissions, ensure safety, and create zero-waste, market-ready solutions.

Simulate & Scale

Test innovations in real-time simulations and operational plants. Digital tools guarantee the impact and viability of our urban biorefinery solutions.

Follow Us!

Scan to visit our social media profiles and our website
www.post-purple.eu

Get in touch

Coordinator: Daniel Puyol Santos (URJC)
daniel.puyol@urjc.es

IMPERIAL

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.